

Structural Study of Mullite prepared from different Systems/Source at different Temperatures with the Aid of Physical Techniques like X-Ray and Ir

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X-Ray and ir spectral studies of mullite obtained from various raw materials by firing at different temperatures are described. The variability of X-ray intensity, if there be any, from different lattice planes of mullite in different mullite samples has been studied. In spite of their similar d values, there are differences in the magnitude of relative intensity from lattice planes in some cases. Ir spectra of mullite is broad in each case, and the spectra of mullite prepared from layer silicates is better defined than the rest.

Attempts have been made to correlate the findings with the chemical and thermal history of the sample as well as with the imperfection of mullite crystal.

ACCOUNTS of the mullitisation in fired soils¹, composition^{2,3} and cell dimensions of mullite², problem of melting/decomposition of mullite⁴, and nature of three types of closely similar crystalline varieties of mullite (α , β and γ) have been reported. Addition of small amounts of an impurity such as Fe_2O_3 or TiO_2 with alumina in the synthesis was capable of producing large variation in lattice spacings of α -mullite. In the literature there are many more references about the formation of solid solution of mullite⁵⁻⁸. Since Taylor⁹ published the results of the X-ray study on mullite, numerous investigations in different aspects were carried out on mullite because of its common occurrence in various ceramic products. In the literature there are a number of references about ir absorption spectra of mullite¹⁰⁻¹² and it was observed that ir bands of mullite are usually broad.

Keeping all these in view, it will be interesting to make a comparative X-ray and ir structural study of mullite formed at high temperature from diverse sources like natural mineral kyanite, from layer silicate like pyrophyllite and Chaibasa clay (where kaolinite is the predominating clay mineral) as well as from synthetic mixture of Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 corresponding to the stoichiometric formula $3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$. In the first three materials there are some foreign oxides other than Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 . As such the role and interaction of these oxides during the formation of mullite from Al_2O_3 and SiO_2 at high temperature envisage an interesting topic for investigation.

Experimental

The mullite samples used in the present study are described in Table 1.

Diffraction tracing of each sample was recorded in Philips PW-1730 X-ray apparatus using Ni filtered CuK_α radiation. The crystalline phases of each sample were identified by the standard method¹³. The d value of mullite along with the relative intensity of each line, taken for comparing with the experimental samples. The content of mullite in the sample was found to increase in the following orders, M-P > M-2 > M > M-3 > M-1.

Results and Discussion

It is found that X-ray characteristics of samples M-1, M-2 and M-3 show some similarities among themselves with regard to d values and there exists a general agreement with respect to their relative intensities which can be satisfactorily compared with the ASTM data of mullite. X-Ray pattern of sample M is nearly similar to the above three samples with the sole exception that the relative intensity of X-ray line due to d value of 2.294 Å in M is slightly greater than the corresponding line in other samples. On the other hand, X-ray patterns of sample M-P is somewhat different, although its d values are quite in agreement with other samples but the relative intensities of some lines differ as compared to the corresponding lines of other samples and ASTM data.

There is the change in relative intensity due to mass absorption coefficient. Some impurities like Fe_2O_3 , TiO_2 , etc. are present in samples M-1, M-2 and M-3 (Table 1). The calculated mass absorption coefficients for Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , CaO , Fe_2O_3 and TiO_2 for CuK_α radiation are 31.8, 34.9, 126.6, 230.8 and 127.4 respectively. Similarly, the mass absorption coefficient of mullite is 33.

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TABLE 1—PREPARATION CONDITION AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF MULLITE SAMPLES

Sample no.	Raw materials	Temp. (°C)/(time of heating, h)	Analysis %									
			SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	TiO ₂	MgO	CaO	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	LOI	
M	Pure Al ₂ O ₃ and SiO ₂ in mole proportion to 3Al ₂ O ₃ .2SiO ₂	1750 (2)	28.20	71.80								
M-1	Pyrophyllite	1400 (4)	61.95	29.10	0.85	0.92	0.70	0.65	0.84	0.13	5.36	
M-2	Kyanite	1400 (4)	40.78	57.16	0.28	0.84	0.02	0.16	0.10	0.14	0.60	
M-3	Chaibasa clay soil (O.T.)	1400 (4)	47.39	32.43	2.91	0.10	2.59	Tr.	3.52	1.04	9.51	
M-P	Same as (M)	Arc furnace for 5 min at >2500°	26.0	73.9								

It is already stated that samples M-1, M-2 and M-3 contain impurity oxide beside Al₂O₃ and SiO₂, while samples M and M-P do not contain any oxide other than Al₂O₃ and SiO₂. In the X-ray pattern of each sample any crystalline phase other than mullite has not been identified. Obviously all these impurities in the first three samples have been volatilised or have entered into solid solution of mullite at 1400°. In case of samples M and M-P, each has been prepared synthetically from pure Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ but their firing temperatures for preparation are wide apart, 1750° and 2500° respectively. The sample M is formed by solid phase interaction at 1750° while M-P is formed from the melt at a temperature much above the melting-decomposition temperature of mullite. In the latter case, mullite is formed by quenching the melt and at that high temperature there is a chance for the loss of SiO₂ from the mixture by evaporation. Teropov and Galakhov¹⁵ proved that SiO₂ did evaporate from Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ mixture at a temperature near the melting point of mullite. As a matter of fact chemical analysis of sample M-P reveals the presence of excess Al₂O₃ (Table 1) more than the formula weight of 3Al₂O₃.2SiO₂. The loss of SiO₂ upsets the 3 : 2 (Al₂O₃, SiO₂) stoichiometry of the mixture. The excess of Al₂O₃ does not exist as corundum because its three strong X-ray lines corresponding to *d* values of 2.085, 2.55 and 1.601 Å are absent. As such the difference in relative intensity of X-ray lines of sample M-P compared to the corresponding X-ray line of ASTM mullite may be accounted for the imperfect crystal growth of mullite by quenching from the melt with subsequent inherent strain in the system.

Ir band due to AlO₄ group^{9,10-12}, around 613 and 561 cm⁻¹, was observed at 600–608 and 560–570 cm⁻¹ respectively for all the samples (Fig. 1). The weak band at 606 cm⁻¹ was almost non-identifiable in samples M and M-P. Similarly AlO₄ bands at 832 and 740 cm⁻¹, SiO₄ bands at 1171, 1120 and 900 cm⁻¹ were observed for all the samples. AlO₄ bands at 810–825, and 735–740 cm⁻¹, and SiO₄ bands at 1165–1180, 1100–1150 and 900–920 cm⁻¹ were also present.

Fig. 1. Ir spectra of mullite samples.

X-Ray diffraction study reveals information on longrange order and the variability of relative intensity from lattice plane of mullite in samples M and M-P arise due to disorder to the mullite structure. Ir spectra of all the samples are similar, however, there are differences in relative intensity and position of the absorption bands. The peak position and the sharpness varied with the composition and the nature of mullite.

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